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**USE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY AMONG
NOVICE TEACHERS**

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INTRODUCTION

Today, due to the impact of LPG and ICT factors, the global trends become local. So to fulfill the global needs of the students, the teachers should be very smart, update and award about the 21st Century, skill. It is direct responsibility of teacher training institute to produce quality teacher to the schools under such circumstances, information and communication technology (ICT) can play an important role in the preparation of quality teachers, the national council for teacher education (NCTE) has put lots of emphasis on its use. From this background, it is very clear that the nature of Traditional Teacher Education program is shifted to ICT related program. It is the paradigm shift due to the global need.

ICT, if used creatively, can make a big difference in the way teachers teach and students learn and can help students acquire 21st century skills like digital literacy, innovative thinking, creativity, sound reasoning and effective communication. ICT can help in enhancing the quality of education through blended learning by supplementing the traditional talk and chalk method of teaching

In recent years we have seen a significant, and long overdue, shift in education from and emphasis on 'teaching' to an emphasis on 'learning'. The focus of attention is now firmly on the learner, their needs, interests and aspirations, at the heart of the education system. This change in focus needs to be welcomed as education is, of course, first and foremost about learners.

So ICT in education is the need of the hour. It has the potential to provide solution to many of the challenges higher education faces today. The common fear that ICT shall replace a teacher is totally unfounded. Realization now seems to be slowly dawning on the teaching community that ICT is primarily to empower them and not to replace them. ICT is, therefore, not to be feared but to be embraced so as to empower our future generations by providing them high quality ICT-enabled education.

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) use the term ICT, or information and communication technologies, to describe:

“...the tools and the processes to access, retrieve, store, organize, manipulate, produce, present and exchange information by electronic and other automated means. These include hardware, software and telecommunications in the forms of personal computers, scanners, digital cameras, phones, faxes, modems, CD and DVD players and recorders, digitized video, radio and TV program, database program and multimedia program.”

1.1 Integration of ICT :

Various competencies are needed to be developed throughout the educational system for ICT integration to be successful. Change is a constant condition in our education system. With coming of the ICT in education there are implications on teacher identity and role. Mere retooling of teacher competencies for specific purposes will not solve the problem. An approach is needed to bring about renaissance in teacher development so that he can effortlessly integrate ICT in teaching learning process.

This Research has tried to identify the use of ICT of student teacher. It has also tried to focus attention on current areas of ICT education that need to be concentrated upon in teacher training institutes. This is important because unless and until we know that what our current teaching in teacher training institutes is producing we cannot effectively integrate the ICT in education system.

2.NEED AND IMPORTANCE

2.1 Need:

- With the help of ICT based education in schools, teachers can play a key role. Training to teachers to use ICT not only for teaching but for developing the mindset for positive approach towards ICT is very important and need of the nation.
- Education system is going through the phase of transition due to introduction of ICT. For smooth transition into the ICT integrated world teachers role is

- indispensable. So this necessitates the development of teachers first, understanding their needs, learning methodologies, anxieties and approach towards learning , this study was necessary.
- In 21st century not only knowledge but professional development plays an critical role. There is need to know if ICT is being used in an effective way so that novice teachers understand the concept and importance of professional development.
- Being a member of teacher community researcher wanted to know at what extent the use of ICT among teacher trainees, for this purpose it was necessary to study.

2.2 Importance

- This research has brought into focus the use of ICT among Novice Teacher.
- This research has helped to identify the focus needed in particular area of ICT e.g. in knowledge, its application, technical handling of hardware, decision making etc.
- This research has brought into focus the ICT awareness among Novice Teacher .
- This research can be helpful in upgrading the ICT syllabus of B.Ed students.
- The teacher trainee will be able to effectively applicative their knowledge in classroom environment.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Use of Information and Communication Technology among teacher trainees

➤ Operational Definition

Use of ICT : Use of ICT means that particular individual (Teacher trainees) can make use of diverse set of technological tools and resources like computers, the internet, social networking, telephony and broadcasting technologies to communicate, disseminate, store, manage, and create new information for personal and professional development.

Novice Teacher: Novice Teacher are the students who are doing B.Ed Course from the Teacher Training institutes affiliated from University of Pune.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the use of ICT among Novice Teachers.
2. To find out the awareness of latest communication media among Novice Teachers.
3. To identify, necessity of Novice Teachers in various field of ICT.

5. ASSUMPTIONS

1. Novice Teachers has knowledge about ICT.
2. Student-teachers are using Technology in their daily routine.
3. There is integration of ICT in education.
4. They have access to Technology in teacher training institute.

6 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

6.1 Method of the Study

Descriptive survey was used for the present study.

6.2 Population

In the present research all the students who were completing B.Ed from University of Pune were the the population of this study..

6.3 Sample

Table No 1 : Sample of the study

No of Colleges	Novice Teachers from each college	Total Sample Selected
04	50	200

In present research 200 Novice Teachers from four B.Ed colleges of University of Pune were taken by Random Sampling Method.

6.4 Tools for Data Collection

Questionnaire

It was consisted of 25 questions on various aspects of use of ICT in education.

6.5 Statistical technique

In the present study percentage, was used to analyze the data.

6.6 Scope

This research will benefited to all the Novice Teachers (students) of B.Ed colleges of Pune University.

6.7 Limitations

- 1) Size of sample was small.

- 2) Students age, their prior knowledge was not controlled .
- 3) Research was taken into consideration the students of year 2012-13 only.
- 4) Data collection tool was developed by the researcher.

6.8 Delimitations

- 1) In this research use of ICT among B.Ed students was studied.
- 2) B.Ed colleges, from University of Pune were taken into consideration.

6.9 Procedure of the study

Survey : To study the use and the needs regarding ICT of Novice Teachers a survey from randomly selected 200 teacher trainees from four colleges was conducted with the help of questionnaire.

- The data collected were organized and analyzed with systematic manner. Following is the example of data organization and analysis.

Table No 2 : To build professional relations

I use to build professional relations	Face book	yahoo	LinkedIn
No. of respondents	104	64	32
Percentage	52%	32%	16%

Analysis -

- From table no 2, 52% of the respondents said that they use social media face book to build professional relationship. 32% of the respondents seem to be using yahoo to build professional relationship. Only 16% of the respondents actually were aware about the professional website LinkedIn and its purpose.
- The analysis of the questionnaire was done in this manner. On the basis of analysis the interpretations and conclusions were obtained.

7 CONCLUSION :

1. Most of Novice teachers were using word processing. 76% respondents have rated themselves high on the word processing skill. The teacher trainees about 70% were well

- aware in accessing internet. When it comes for searching information on net only 10% feel that are really good at it.
2. The social media face book to build professional relationship is used by 52% of the respondents . Only 16% of the respondents were aware about the professional website LinkedIn and its purpose.
 3. Only 18.5% of the novice teachers would make use of blogs to share academic work while most of them still use email attachments to do the same.
 4. About 74% of the teacher trainees take help from learned person to install Microsoft office in computer.
 5. About 64% of the respondents said that they will report the matter of hacking and bullying to cyber cell. While 12% of respondents said that they will never open that account again.
 6. For collecting information for survey work 72% Novice Teachers would prefer online survey. While 11.5% of the respondents said that they will prefer to use pint media for collecting information for survey.
 7. Teacher trainees vary in their knowledge and awareness about various aspects of ICT. When it comes to word processing they are well aware about it whereas they need help with spreadsheets and searching information on net. There are other aspects like searching information with key words on net, use of ICT in professional development, etc. where they need to get some help.
 8. Large percentage of teacher trainees needs to be guided about the latest in the technology. Most of them had heard about cloud computing and 3-G but not aware what it is. They need to be made aware of usage of blogs for communication and academic purposes.
 9. Novice Teachers need help when it comes to use of spreadsheets, preparing PowerPoint presentations, communicating through blogs, building relationships. Teacher trainees are well prepared to work in the ICT environment and respond to situations in immediacy.

8 DISCUSSION:

The findings of the present study make it very clear that teacher trainees need to focus on certain areas of ICT. In the research conducted by Manoj Kumar Sinha it was found that teachers

were more comfortable in using word processing. In the present researcher found that teacher trainees are most comfortable in using word processing whereas, in the study conducted by Sasikala it was found that teacher of D.T.ED had little knowledge of computers. Teachers are apathetic and ignorant to use computer. They had language problem and do not have sufficient confidence to use computer.

In the present study researcher found out that teacher trainees have confidence in using computers. The teacher trainees were quite active on social networking sites. Miss.Rajani S. Telore too found out that teacher trainees were quite active on social networking.

9 RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Novice Teachers should be made more computer savvy.
2. Ample practice should be incorporated not only for submissions of files and practical's but in daily learning as well.
3. Mere Teaching of basic computer literacy such as the traditional operating system, word processor spreadsheet, database and telecommunications is not enough. In every profession there is a level of literacy beyond general computer literacy. Professional literacy is best learned in context.
4. Teacher education institutions also need to develop strategies and plans to enhance the teaching-learning process within teacher education program and to assure that all future teachers are well prepared to use the new tools (ICT) for learning practically.
5. ICT should be used in creating environments in which a student can practice new ideas.
6. ICT demands responsibility in their behaviour towards personal life of others. ICT teacher trainees should be aware of the ethical issues, so that they can be ready for incidents that may arise in the classroom.

10. EDUCATIONAL IMPLECATION

1. The survey result puts light on understanding of the needs, learning methodologies, anxieties and approach towards learning of teacher trainees.
2. The present study has bring forth areas which need to be focused in teacher training institutes .

3. It may give direction to the teacher trainee the importance of ICT for professional development.
4. The results may be helpful for teacher trainee who conducts computer based practical.
5. It highlights the importance and need of the moral and ethical education in the needs today.
6. It may also contribute in the construction of B.Ed. syllabus. The benchmark of ICT elements may be defined by the result of the study.

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